

Florian Thiery & Sophie C. Schmidt

Linked Reindeers?

A Linked Open Data
approach for rock art in Alta

Karin Tansem, VAM World Heritage Rock Art Centre - Alta Museum CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 (2005)

As a member of the German CAA Chapter, it is an honor to have the possibility to be part of the CAA-N community.

Hej! My name is Lasse.
I am a reindeer from
the North Cape...

I met Florian on his
Scandinavian trip in
summer 2019.

I want to travel with
you to my homeland
and the wonderful
Rock Art in Alta.

On my journey I met a lot of wonderful friends who showed me a lot of cool digital methods in archaeology...

In Western Europe
(Germany and Austria) I
got in touch with a
group of young Linked
Open Data enthusiasts.

Research Squirrel Engineers

Sophie & Florian
@idhrenil @fthierygeo

Martina & Timo

We are Research Squirrels
and interested in Open
Science and **Linked Data**

Research Squirrel Engineers

<http://squirrel.link>

local (offline)

online

online & open

part of LOD

Not many databases are online. Few of them are openly available and accessible. Even less are part of the Linked Open Data Cloud.

I want to compare all rock art paintings between 4000 and 2700 BCE

part of LOD?

Karin Tanscm, VAM World Heritage Rock Art Centre - Alta Museum CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 (2005)

online & open

comparative analysis of records across multiple datasets is difficult

Linked Data?

the goal: archaeological data as part of the Linked Data Cloud

The Research Squirrels
want to enhance Linked
Data usage in
Archaeology.

SPARQL Unicorn

SPARQL Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Ogi-Ogham

The *SPARQL Unicorn*
was born at...

CHECK OBJECT INTEGRITY
CAA 2019
KRAKÓW 23-27 April

© Stary Port, Kraków

Community

**Do you know
Wikidata?**

- ❖ A free and open knowledge base
→ everybody can add and edit
- ❖ **central storage for structured data of Wikimedia projects**

data in Wikidata is:

- ❖ **available under a free license (CC 0)**
- ❖ **multilingual**
- ❖ **accessible to humans and machines (GUI & API & SPARQL)**
- ❖ **exportable using standard formats (JSON, RDF, XML)**
- ❖ **interlinked to other open data sets on the LOD Cloud**

What is Wikidata?

Most of the tools require knowledge of SPARQL. Queries can become very complex.


```
1 SELECT ?date ?work ?workLabel ?topics (GROUP_CONCAT(DISTINCT
separator=" // " ) AS ?places) (GROUP_CONCAT(?authorLabel; sepa
authorstrings) (GROUP_CONCAT(?editorLabel; separator= " - " )
2 WITH {
3 SELECT DISTINCT ?work WHERE {
4 ?work wdt:P921 / (wdt:P361+ | wdt:P1269+ | (wdt:P31* / wd
5 }
6 } AS %works
7 WITH {
8 SELECT (MIN(?dates) as ?datetime) ?work (GROUP_CONCAT(?topi
9 INCLUDE %works
10 ?work wdt:P921 ?topic .
11 FILTER NOT EXISTS {
12 ?topic wdt:P31 wd:Q839954} .
13 FILTER NOT EXISTS {
14 ?topic wdt:P31 wd:Q220659}
15 OPTIONAL { ?work wdt:P577 ?dates . }
16
17 ?topic rdfs:label ?topic_label . FILTER (lang(?topic_labe
18 }
19 GROUP BY ?work
20 } AS %result
21 WHERE {
22 INCLUDE %result
23
24 OPTIONAL { ?work wdt:P50 ?author .
25 ?author rdfs:label ?authorLabel . FILTER (lang(?a
26 }
27 # no extra label assignment here, because we already have a
28 OPTIONAL { ?work wdt:P2093 ?authorstring . }
29 OPTIONAL { ?work wdt:P98 ?editor .
30 ?editor rdfs:label ?editorLabel . FILTER (lang(?e
31 }
32 OPTIONAL { ?work wdt:P123 ?publisher . }
33
34 #collect related places (are in topic list; are instance of
35 OPTIONAL {?work wdt:P921 ?place
```


How can I help
researchers without
knowledge of SPARQL in
using community driven
data from Wikidata?

#LittleMinion
#SPARQLUnicorn

develop a 'SPARQL unicorn' as little minion to help researchers

**SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin
- a Linked Data Access Point for QGIS**

The screenshot shows the QGIS interface with a map of Europe. A layer named 'unicorn Airports Germany' is active, displaying red dots representing airports. The 'SPARQL Unicorn Wikidata Plugin' dialog is open, showing the following configuration:

- Query: Interlink, Enrich
- Select endpoint: Wikidata --> ?geo requir
- Or: Load From File
- layer name: unicorn_Airports_Germany
- Layer concept: airport(Q1246784)
- Query Templates: Item+Label
- Constraint by Area Type: city (Q515)
- Area: (empty)
- Constraint By BBOX: (checked)

The dialog contains a SPARQL query:

```
# Example: Airports in Germany
SELECT ?label ?geo ?item WHERE {
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q1246784; #Airport
  ?range wd:Q183; #Germany
  wdt:P625 ?geo;
  rdfs:label ?label.
  FILTER((LANG(?label)) = "en")
} LIMIT 100
```

Buttons at the bottom of the dialog include 'add layer', 'load unicorn layers', 'unicorn_Airports_Germany', 'Export Loaded Layer as TTL', and 'Schließen'.

simplified querying of Semantic Web data sources

**Be part of the Wikidata community!
An example on how to do this...**

UCC Stone Corridor, Stone 4, C1C 81 (Florian Thiery) CC BY 4.0

R.A.S. Macalister, Corpus Inscriptionum Insularum Celticarum, vol. I (1945)

... is the Linked Ogham Stones 'squirrel' Project.

link to existing information: **OSM**

input into *wikidata*, link to existing datasets in *wikidata*

extract information on ogham stones: **townland, barony, county**

extract enriched data with the help of the SPARQL unicorn

Macálistér 1945

further analysis with open source software

From analog catalogues to LOD and further...

<https://openrefine.org/>
<https://tools.wmflabs.org/quickstatements/#/>

OpenRefine Stones_Export_17021020_7.csv

#	Wikitext	lang_en	label_en	description_en	alias_en	lang_de	label_de	description_de	alias_de	P252_coord	P189_place	P17_country	P188_c
1	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
2	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
3	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
4	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
5	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
6	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
7	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
8	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
9	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
10	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
11	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
12	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
13	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
14	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
15	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
16	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
17	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
18	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
19	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en
20	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en	en

Wikidata interface showing various property editors:

- Label:** en, label_en | of: override if present
- Statements:** part of: Ogi-Ogam Project
- country:** P17_country
- coordinate location:** P252_coord, subject has role: archaeological site
- description:** GIECQIAR MUCIO EURQIINOMAS
- location of discovery:** G8538914 (G8538914)
- part of:** Ogi-Ogam Project (Q7673955)
- coordinate location:** 52°E 41.00' N, 7°30' 00' W

QuickStatements interface showing a list of statements:

Stapel "ogham" auf Wikidata von Fthiergeo [Stapel]

Status: 0% (0) von 308 erledigt

- en: CHC 295 (Q7082999) | Label: en:"en:CHC 295"
- en: CHC 295 (Q7082999) | Statement: part of (P581): Ogi-Ogam Project (Q7082999)
- en: CHC 295 (Q7082999) | Statement: country (P17): Ireland (Q27)
- en: CHC 295 (Q7082999) | Statement: Sources to: country (P17): Ireland (Q27) | stated in (P244): Corpus Inscriptionum Insularum Celticarum Vol.1 (Q7056237)
- en: CHC 295 (Q7082999) | Statement: coordinate location (P625): 52.111389;7.6 (on Earth)
- en: CHC 295 (Q7082999) | Statement: Qualifier to: coordinate location (P625): 52.111389;7.6 (on Earth) | subject has role (P296): archaeological site (Q89954)
- en: CHC 295 (Q7082999) | Statement: Sources to: coordinate location (P625): 52.111389;7.6 (on Earth) | stated in (P244): Corpus Inscriptionum Insularum Celticarum Vol.1 (Q7056237)
- en: CHC 295 (Q7082999) | Statement: location of discovery (P188): Knockboy Towland (Q8538914)
- en: CHC 295 (Q7082999) | Statement: Sources to: location of discovery (P188): Knockboy Towland (Q8538914) | stated in (P244): Corpus Inscriptionum Insularum Celticarum Vol.1 (Q7056237)
- en: CHC 295 (Q7082999) | Statement: location of discovery (P188): County Waterford (Q84494)

Wikidata import using OpenRefine & QuickStatements

<http://ogham.link>

Wikidata View

<https://w.wiki/HRe>

I could do that for
my rock art
reindeer friends
in Alta as well!

Karin Tanscm, VAM World Heritage Rock Art Centre - Alta Museum CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 (2005).

The image shows a topographic map of the Alta region in Norway, featuring brown and tan terrain with blue water bodies. Several red location pins are placed on the map. On the right side, there is a search interface with a list of locations and a search button.

Alta	
Hjemmeluft	
Apana Gård	velg feltnr ▼
Apanes	velg feltnr ▼
Bergbukten	velg feltnr ▼
Bergheim	velg feltnr ▼
Decca	velg feltnr ▼
MBA	velg feltnr ▼
Ole Pedersen	velg feltnr ▼
Amtmannsnes	velg feltnr ▼
Isnestoften	velg feltnr ▼
Kongshus	velg feltnr ▼
Kråknes	velg feltnr ▼
Kåfjord	velg del ▼
Storsteinen	velg feltnr ▼
Svartskog	velg feltnr ▼
Tollevik	velg feltnr ▼
Transfarelv	velg feltnr ▼
Årøya	velg feltnr ▼

Søk i arkivet

Google

Map source: © Kartverket

Das Bild ist möglicherweise urheberrechtlich geschützt. 2 km

Nutzungsbedingungen

Open Data Website - altarockart.no

The main map is a topographic map of the Bergbukten area. It shows a trail marked with a series of purple teardrop icons. The map includes contour lines and shaded relief. A legend in the bottom right corner lists various locations with a 'velg feltnr' (select field number) dropdown menu.

Alta	
Hjimmeluft	
Apana Gård	velg feltnr ▼
Apanes	velg feltnr ▼
Bergbukten	velg feltnr ▼
Bergheim	velg feltnr ▼
Decca	velg feltnr ▼
MBA	velg feltnr ▼
Ole Pedersen	velg feltnr ▼
Amtmannsnes	velg feltnr ▼
Isnestoften	velg feltnr ▼
Kongshus	velg feltnr ▼
Kråknes	velg feltnr ▼
Kåfjord	velg del ▼
Storsteinen	velg feltnr ▼
Svartskog	velg feltnr ▼
Tollevik	velg feltnr ▼
Transfarelv	velg feltnr ▼
Arøya	velg feltnr ▼

[Søk i arkivet](#)

An inset map in the bottom left corner shows the location of Bergbukten within a larger geographical context. It features a legend with two lines: a purple line for 1.2 km and a yellow line for 3 km. A yellow line traces a path around a lake, with labels for 'Panslegg carvings' and 'Steinhest carvings'. A yellow square with a black 'no' symbol and the text 'Stay on the pathway!' is also present. The 'Alta Museum' is marked at the bottom of the inset. The Google logo is visible in the bottom left corner of the inset.

Map source: © Kartverket

altarockart.no: Bergbukten

Browse in Norwegian

Browse in English

Nach oben | Browse in English > Hjemmeluft > Bergbukten > Bergbukten 1 898 Treffer

Sortieren nach Zuletzt modifiziert ↓

Alles reduzieren

Sites and Panels

Kein

Filter

Figures

- Axe
- Bear
- Bear den
- Bear track
- Bird
- Boat
- Bow
- Dog/Wolf
- Drum
- Elk
- Elk head staff
- Elk track
- Fish
- Fishing line
- Footprint/S...

the open altarockart.no fotoweb archive

Karin Tansem, VAM World Heritage Rock Art Centre - Alta Museum CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 (2015)

Mappelet 1
Karteneid, 1:10000
1:10000
1:10000

<http://altarockart.no/fotoweb/archives/5002-Browse-in-English/Indekserte%20bilder/aaa20151204runo029.pdf#info>

Karin Tansem, VAM World Heritage Rock Art Centre - Alta Museum CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 (2012)

ALTA MUSEUM

World Heritage
Rock Art Centre

link to existing
information in
altarockart.no

extract information on rock
art carvings:
location, depictions

altarockart.no

input into wikidata,
link to existing
datasets in wikidata

extract enriched
data with the help
of the **SPARQL
unicorn**

further analysis
with open
source software

- Main page
- Community portal
- Project chat
- Create a new Item
- Recent changes
- Random Item
- Query Service
- Nearby
- Help
- Donate

- Lexicographical data
- Create a new Lexeme
- Recent changes

- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Cite this page
- Concept URI

Item Discussion

Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (Q82685468)

Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1

edit

In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1	Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1
German	No label defined	No description defined
Polish	No label defined	No description defined
French	No label defined	No description defined

All entered languages

Statements

instance of archaeological site
 0 references

rock art
 0 references

petroglyph
 0 references

Q82685468

country

Norway

edit

0 references

+ add reference

+ add value

located in the administrative territorial entity

Alta

edit

0 references

+ add reference

+ add value

coordinate location

edit

69°56'56.159"N, 23°10'40.393"E

0 references

+ add reference

+ add value

Item: [Discussion](#)

Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-85) (Q100149218)

Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (C-85) [edit](#)

[In more languages](#)

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-85)	Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (C-85)	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

Instance of	 rock art edit
	 0 references + add reference
 petroglyph	 0 references + add reference
	 0 references + add reference
 carving	 0 references + add reference
	 0 references + add reference
 archaeological artifact	 0 references + add reference
	 0 references + add value

depicts	 reindeer 0 references + add reference
	 antlers 0 references + add reference
hoof	 0 references + add value
	 0 references + add value
collection	 Rock Art of Alta Collection edit
	 0 references + add reference
non-free artwork image URL	 http://altarockart.no/fotoweb/cache/5002/indekserte%20bilder/201007271aju214.146d3f7e.m800.xEY11v_TjYzYgJWEZ.JPG edit
	 0 references + add reference
	 0 references + add value

Q100149218

- Main page
- Community portal
- Project chat
- Create a new Item
- Recent changes
- Random Item
- Query Service
- Nearby
- Help
- Donate

- Lexicographical data
- Create a new Lexeme
- Recent changes

- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Cite this page
- Concept URI

Item [Discussion](#)

Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-63) (Q100151497)

Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (C-63) [edit](#)

▼ In more languages

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-63)	Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (C-63)	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of	 rock art edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
	 petroglyph edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
 carving edit	
	▼ 0 references + add reference
 archaeological artifact edit	
	▼ 0 references + add reference

depicts	 reindeer edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
	 antlers edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
	+ add value
collection	 Rock Art of Alta Collection edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
	+ add value
non-free artwork image URL	 http://altarockart.no/fotoweb/cache/5002/indekserte%20bilder/2012/03211aj431.14e40ef30.m800.xykw3lIEK2bNjzda4.jpg edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
	+ add value

Q100151497

Cool idea? Help us –
it is a collaborative
Squirrel project!

<https://github.com/Research-Squirrel-Engineers/alta-rock-art>

Research Squirrel Engineers

And join us at the
**CAA SIG Data
Dragon!**

Data Dragon

Data Dragon

Special Interest Group

**CAA SIG on “Semantics and LOUD
in Archaeology”**

*“We would like to further establish **Linked Data** in **archeology**, enable **beginners** to use and produce Linked Data, invite other **scientists** for discussion, and embed LOD as an **important topic** through an **SIG** at the **CAA** conference and **community**.”*

Cya at CAA 2021
Linked Data
Session
“Hic sunt dracones”

CAA 2021
Digital
Crossroads

14-18 June, Limassol, Cyprus

Cyprus
University of
Technology

Data Dragon

Thx!

Any questions?

Mail

hi@squirrel.link

Wikidata

[Q71933512](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q71933512)

[Q66606154](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q66606154)

Research Squirrel Engineers

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